

ZT&T: Secure service session management using blockchain-based tokens in Zero Trust Networks.

Javier Jose Diaz Rivera^{1,3}, Waleed Akbar², Talha Ahmed Khan^{1,4}, Afaq Muhammad^{1,4} and Wang-Cheol Song^{1,4*}

¹Jeju National University, 102 Jejudaehak-ro, Jeju-si, 63243, Jeju-do, Republic of Korea.

²Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss 7, Castelldefels, 08860, Barcelona, Spain.

³Department of Electronic Engineering.

⁴Department of Computer Engineering.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): kingiron@gmail.com;

Contributing authors: shaifvier@gmail.com;

waleedwali786@gmail.com; talhajadun@gmail.com;

afaq24@gmail.com;

Abstract

In today's interconnected world, the line that separates the network perimeter can no longer be identified. This has led to the development of Zero Trust Networking (ZTN) and Software Defined Perimeter (SDP) concepts, which aim to extend the perimeter of trust to every entity connected to the network regardless of their physical location. However, implementing complex security mechanisms and constant trust assurance for every interaction can be challenging. One solution is integrating blockchain technology into Zero Trust to provide security. Blockchain offers features such as data decentralization, anonymity, cryptography, and immutable record of transactions that can be utilized. This work proposes a mechanism for secure service session management using blockchain capabilities. Non-Fungible-Tokens (NFT) are applied to access and provider tokens representing a policy agreement for service consumption. These tokens are mapped to the public addresses of entities registered in the blockchain. The proposal is realized through an open-source Zero Trust platform and a private Ethereum blockchain.

Keywords: zero-trust, SDP, blockchain, sessions, NFT

1 Introduction

Recent advancements in network technology, like 5G networks and cloud/edge computing, have heightened the demand for network adaptability and capability [1, 2]. The key enablers for this are Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV), which allow current network technologies to expand according to service demands [3]. This is primarily accomplished by emphasizing the network’s programmable features rather than its physical components. This shift also highlights the need for greater attention to securing the network [4, 5].

In traditional network architecture, security measures are established for internal and external access based on a defined secure boundary. The physical location of network components, such as firewalls and routers, establishes this boundary, which can encompass a LAN, Campus Network, WAN, or Internet connection. This security model trusts any activity within the network boundary while only verifying external access. This concept is referred to as the “castle-and-moat” model [6, 7]. Before the introduction of SDN and NFV, it was relatively straightforward to establish secure boundaries as network components and services had a physical location, allowing for effective security policies. However, this model has a fundamental flaw in that once an attacker breaches the network boundary, they can access assets and cause damage.

The Zero Trust Network (ZTN) architecture was proposed [8] as a solution to the security weaknesses of the castle-and-moat model and to provide enhanced security for modern networks that utilize SDN and NFV. ZTN emphasizes the need for secure access to all network resources, regardless of location, through strict verification, access control, and constant network activity monitoring. The ZTN architecture includes various deployment options, such as micro-segmentation, network orchestration, SDN, NFV, and other approaches [9]. One of the recommended ZTN approaches is Software Defined Perimeter (SDP), which is outlined in the architecture document [10, 11]. SDP closely follows the integration of SDN and NFV, creating a secure network overlay managed by an SDP controller responsible for user/device verification and management of security policies governing access and denial of services. These policies are enforced by SDP gateways at endpoints connecting to the network.

ZTN prioritizes continuous verification of entities and their access rights instead of relying on a single trust point. However, traditional methods of session access control, such as cookies and session tokens, which are commonly used to identify and authenticate clients, do not align with the principles of ZTN [12]. These methods involve assigning a unique identification object to the client, which is then sent back to the server for every request, allowing

the server to look up the corresponding session information and confirm if the client is authorized to access the requested resources. Despite their usefulness, these forms of access control are still at risk of security breaches, such as cross-site request forgery (CSRF) attacks, where a malicious actor can steal a user's cookies and send harmful requests to the server, or a man-in-the-middle attack where the attacker intercepts and uses a valid token to gain unauthorized access to protected resources [13, 14].

Session tokens for ZTN can be enhanced by implementing features such as expiration and revocation in case of security breaches, binding to specific users, secure distribution, and monitoring for any misuse or anomalies [15]. To achieve this goal, distributed ledger technologies like blockchain can be employed to store session token information securely and ensure continuity in case of server or database failures [16]. Additionally, the cryptographic key functionality of blockchain can be combined with the identity management of ZTN for the unique identification of users and mapping them to session tokens and the immutable transaction ledger of the blockchain can be utilized to keep track of all activities associated with the usage and misuse of session tokens [17].

This manuscript is an expanded version of a previous paper presented at the 6th Cyber Security in Networking Conference (CSNet, 2022) [17]. Compared to the original paper, this work's main contributions include an updated literature review section, a more detailed policy definition process, added explanations for token creation and provisioning, and expanded experimental results. The research combines a private Ethereum blockchain, built using the Hyperledger Besu open-source project, with an SDP overlay for ZTN (OpenZiti). The blockchain is used for the unique identification of endpoints (Clients and Service providers) through Ethereum accounts (public/private keys and public address) and secure storage of identity information via smart contracts. A decentralized application for Zero Trust through the use of tokens (ZT&T) creates secure access policies based on the information stored on the blockchain, such as roles and service definitions linked to unique identities. These policies are encapsulated in Non-Fungible Tokens (NFT) metadata, which represents access tokens (when mapped to a client's public address) and provider tokens (when mapped to a service provider's public address). Only registered identities that hold these tokens are able to participate in the ZTN. The blockchain implementation ensures that session tokens are stored securely and facilitates proof-of-ownership verification for access/provider tokens during each service session. Moreover, it allows keeping track of the tokens' validity period to enable automatic expiration.

The paper is structured as follows: In section 2, related work is presented; section 3 provides information about the system; section 4 presents the experiments and results; and finally, section 5 concludes the manuscript.

2 Related Work

The use of blockchain in cybersecurity is based on principles such as confidentiality, integrity, and availability [18], achieved through cryptographic hashing techniques and an immutable chain of blocks. These key features make blockchain a strong candidate for integration into ZTN systems. However, there are concerns about the computational overhead caused by transaction replication across multiple nodes and the low throughput of current blockchain technologies [19, 20]. Nevertheless, recent research has explored opportunities to integrate blockchain with Zero Trust. In [21], a blockchain-based data storage scheme (S-BDS) was proposed for Zero Trust in the Internet of Things (IoT) networks. The focus of the research was to establish a trust mechanism between devices, which can be addressed through cryptographic key management and digital signatures provided by a distributed blockchain. The proposal relies on distributed data storage via blockchain, where only verified devices/users can access the data. Verification is done through the blockchain's public/private key representing the identity of IoT devices within the ZTN. To address performance issues, the authors applied a technique called “sharding,” which involves dividing the main blockchain network into subnetworks, or “shards,” containing a subset of nodes that do not need to replicate all transactions to other shards. This approach reduces the number of processed transactions and increases throughput. The authors' considerations for integrating blockchain into a ZTN system align with the work proposed in our manuscript. Blockchain can provide unique identity management and verification through its native cryptographic keys. Additionally, the performance of blockchain can be improved not only by using the sharding technique but also by utilizing different consensus mechanisms other than Proof of Work (PoW).

The authors in [22] describe a research to address the growing concern of security threats among active sessions in the IoT environment. The researchers propose using blockchain technology to provide continuous and non-intrusive authentication for IoT devices. The CAB-IoT solution includes a fog node layer to handle the limitations of IoT resources, a trust module based on face recognition using machine learning to detect anomalies and abnormal access, and mutual authentication between end-users and fog nodes. The trust is established by access tokens issued by smart contracts in the blockchain. The study's results demonstrate a lightweight continuous authentication solution that was tested in a real-world environment for accurate results. However the specifications of the token standard used in the manuscript are not disclosed.

In [23], the authors put forward a blockchain-based information-sharing scheme for Zero Trust IoT that uses an authentication protocol to verify the ad-hoc endpoints sharing information within the network. The smart contracts detect and eliminate potentially fabricated information, and a penalty system evaluates the ad-hoc devices. This approach denies access to unauthenticated devices and enforces penalties on misbehaving ones. The authors' solution relies on the authentication mechanism for IoT devices which uses the public/private keys generated by the blockchain, similar to the research

motivation outlined in [21]. However, the authors also express concerns about the framework's performance due to the computational overhead of blockchain technology. Even though the Ethereum blockchain functionality was utilized, the authors used a local test blockchain created with Ganache [24] for deployment, which does not fully reflect the performance and transaction execution costs discussed in the manuscript.

In [25], the authors conducted a systematic review on enhancing Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA) for endpoints using blockchain. The review paper examines the various Zero Trust approaches adopted by the industry and research groups to implement ZTN. It highlights the "Achilles heel" of ZTA, where compromised endpoints that have already been authenticated and authorized can be used for malicious activities. The paper examines the use of blockchain-based intrusion detection systems to verify the integrity of endpoints in a Zero Trust architecture. It provides an analysis of different blockchain types (Permissionless, Permissioned), consensus mechanisms (PoW, Proof of Stake, Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance), and blockchain properties, with a comparative evaluation. The authors conclude that most of the research on integrating blockchain with Zero Trust is still theoretical, but the core principles of ZTA, such as "never trust but verify," align well with blockchain's operation of transaction validation, consensus, and integrity through ledger immutability.

The authors in [26] proposed a model for securing cookies through NFT and smart contracts using blockchain. The author's mechanism relies on a server identifying users utilizing an NFT to verify claims of ownership as an identifier and generating a session ticket with an attached cookie for every user request. When a user desires to access a resource in a network, the mechanism verifies the cookies sent by the user from the session ticket by executing a transaction in the blockchain network, which checks the validity of the session ticket. The security of the mechanism is enforced by applying the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) to guarantee the integrity of the session ticket that contains the cookies alongside the unique identifier of the user associated with the ticket. Although NFTs are used to guarantee the identities of the users, an alternative implementation could be used to represent the session ticket as an NFT associated with a user. This modified implementation could improve the cookie validation performance, which incurs delays as the authors execute a blockchain transaction every time a user sends a cookie to a server, regardless of the session expiration. Instead, by associating the cookies to the NFTs, the verification can be executed by read-only queries, considerably improving the performance as blockchain transactions do not hinder the time to process a request.

Lastly, in [27], the authors suggested a secure blockchain-based access control (SBAC) framework for information-centric networks. SBAC uses a blockchain-based access token mechanism to control access to content. Under the proposed mechanism, content providers (CPs) advertise their services on the network, and content requesters (CQs) use an access token to access these services. Smart contracts handle the generation, transfer, and verification of

access tokens through interactions with the blockchain. CPs and CQs are entities identified by their blockchain public/private keys, and their blockchain public addresses are used as targets for blockchain transactions. This mechanism aligns with the ZTN principles of constant verification, although it is not explicitly mentioned. The paper provides detailed information about the logic used to achieve secure access control. However, it does not discuss the actual blockchain token implementation used for the access tokens. The authors used the Ethereum blockchain for experimentation, which offers several standards for creating blockchain tokens [28], such as the ERC-20 and the ERC-721. The ERC-721, also known as the non-fungible token standard, defines a unique identifier for each generated token, which can be paired with programmatic metadata to acquire unique properties. Table 1 provides an overview of the significant methods and contributions of the studies described in the related work.

The proposed work in this manuscript aims to identify endpoints (clients and service providers) using blockchain public/private keys as described in [21, 23, 27]. Additionally, it utilizes a blockchain-based access/provider token approach to ensure secure use of network services in a Zero Trust Network (ZTN). The authorization of network participants is further strengthened by implementing a permissioned Ethereum blockchain, and the performance of the blockchain system is improved by using a Proof of Authority (PoA) consensus mechanism. The main contributions of this paper are:

- Granting access to endpoints (clients and services) using permissioned blockchain records.
- Defining service policies using smart contracts on the blockchain.
- Implementing the ERC-721 token standard, where the token metadata includes the service policy for defining access and provider tokens.
- Ensuring safe transfer of access/provider tokens to authorized endpoints through the use of NFT transactions.
- Ending service sessions based on the expiration time included in the access token metadata.

Table 1 Summary of the related work studies

Research	Year	Description	Key contribution	Blockchain
Lyu et al. [27]	2020	Blockchain-based access control framework for secure content sharing.	Matching-based access control model and blockchain-based access token mechanism.	Ethereum (Proof of Stake)
Alevizos et al. [25]	2021	Examination of various approaches for integrating blockchain into zero trust systems.	Extensive analysis of blockchain technologies with comparative evaluation.	Undisclosed
Liu et al. [23]	2022	The use of blockchain to securely facilitate data sharing in a zero trust IoT environment.	Use of smart contracts to authenticate IoT devices and maintain a fair penalty system.	Ethereum (Ganache)
Hussain et al. [22]	2022	A blockchain-based continuous authentication solution for an IoT environment.	The use of face recognition and blockchain-based access tokens to authenticate users.	Private Ethereum (Proof of Authority)
Wang et al. [21]	2022	Establishment of trust between IoT devices for distributed data storage.	Blockchain-based verification, and sharding.	Undisclosed blockchain using Insertable Vector Commitment (IVC) scheme
Shah et al. [26]	2022	Securing cookies using blockchain, smart contracts and NFTs.	ECDSA for integrity of session tickets, use of NFTs for proof of claims of ownership of identities.	Undisclosed
ZT&T	2023	Blockchain-based secure network access framework that leverages NFTs to authorize endpoints and maintain service sessions uniquely.	Smart contract-driven service policy definition, NFT implementation for embedding policies in tokens, and automatic service session termination based on NFT expiration.	Private permissioned Ethereum (Proof of Authority)

3 System Information

Fig. 1 System components of ZT&T

The system proposed in this manuscript includes a permission-based blockchain network capable of executing smart contracts, a decentralized application (dApp) for managing service sessions, and a secure network overlay (OpenZiti) where clients and service providers utilizing the blockchain can securely communicate. Fig. 1 illustrates the components of the system, where clients and service providers connecting to the ZTN are provided with the necessary access/provider tokens ($\alpha\tau|\rho\tau$) for initiating and maintaining connections for service sessions. The components of the system can be described as follows:

- Permissioned blockchain:** A blockchain that is compatible with the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) [29], which is capable of executing smart contracts for programmable logic. The decentralized and unchangeable permissions form the foundation of trust for the system proposed in this manuscript. Access to this blockchain is controlled, and endpoint authentication is managed through interaction with the *identity management smart contract*, which validates the credentials of entities attempting to access the blockchain. While the detailed design and implementation of this process

are informed by the work presented in [30], they are not within the scope of the current research.

- **Session management dApp:** Communicates with the blockchain and secure network overlay to establish service policies within the blockchain and generate access/provider tokens. Smart contract functionality manages token creation and interaction with the blockchain. The dApp includes the functionality for automatically ending service sessions (through interaction with the secure network overlay) by checking the metadata status within the tokens.
- **Secure network overlay:** A network overlay that implements Zero Trust features as a Software Defined Perimeter. The overlay manages secure control traffic utilizing an SDP controller and SDP Gateways. The present work considers the open-source project *OpenZiti* [31] for the overlay functionality. The *service session management dApp* can access management APIs to control ongoing sessions.
- **Client and Service Providers:** Endpoints that connect to the network overlay to establish secure end-to-end connections. Each endpoint is identified by a blockchain account that includes a blockchain private key (*BPrK*), blockchain public key (*BPuK*), and a public address (*BPAddr*). In order to access the ZTN, the blockchain identification must be verified by the permissioned blockchain. Without the proper blockchain account, clients cannot participate in the ZTN.

A brief description of the interaction between the components of the proposed system is depicted in Fig. 2. The initial step involves registering policy information in the *blockchain*, which is then converted into overlay configurations by the *session management dApp*. *Clients* and *service providers* initiate connections to the *secure network overlay*, identifying themselves using their *BPAddr*. Subsequently, the *secure network overlay* communicates with the *session management dApp* to validate the policy corresponding to the requesting *client* or *service provider*. If a policy aligns with the endpoints' request, the *session management dApp* interacts with the *blockchain* to generate session tokens, associating them with the endpoints' *BPAddr*. Following this, the *secure network overlay*, through interaction with the *session management dApp*, verifies the session tokens' validity for each open session, thereby determining connection approval or denial based on the tokens' expiration status. More details about these interactions are presented in the subsections 3.2, 3.3, 3.4.

3.1 Access/Provider Token Definition

Blockchain-based tokens regulate which endpoints are permitted to initiate and sustain a service session within the ZTN. The tokens are created per the ERC-721 standard for EVM-based blockchains. Table 2 illustrates the structure of the ERC-721 tokens, which are composed of two components: the token metadata and the token ownership.

Fig. 2 Example interaction sequence among the components in the proposed system

The metadata of the tokens includes information like the token's *name* and *symbol*, which come from the smart contract used to create them. The *name* is a detailed description of the token, while the *symbol* is an acronym. Each token has a unique *tokenId*, which makes it distinct from others. Additionally, the *tokenURI* field holds extra data in the form of a string. Our proposed system incorporates information about service policies into the *tokenURI* field. The *tokenURI* is structured in a JSON format as $\{ "tokenType": number, "policyId": string, "policyHash": string, "expTime": number \}$.

The *tokenURI* field includes various attributes that determine the kind of token generated. The *tokenType* attribute is set to 1 for access tokens and 2 for service provider tokens, the *policyId* is used to identify a specific service policy within the blockchain, the *policyHash* holds a hash of the defined service policy, and *expTime* is an expiration date set as a Unix type timestamp in Coordinated Universal Time (UTC) format. The ownership of a token is established by linking it to the *BPAddr* of a client/service provider via smart contract functions such as *mint()* and *burn()*. Our proposed system does not permit the transfer of tokens between endpoints. Instead, authorized clients and service providers delegate the management of the tokens to the *service session management dApp* using the *setApprovalForAll()* smart contract function. This delegation applies to all existing and future tokens.

Table 2 ERC-721 Token smart contract functions

Token Metadata	<i>name()</i>	Name of the token
	<i>symbol()</i>	Acronym of the token
	<i>tokenURI()</i>	<i>tokenType</i> , <i>policyId</i> , <i>policyHash</i> and <i>expTime</i>
Token Ownership	<i>ownerOf()</i>	Returns the <i>BPAddr</i> of the entity holding the token
	<i>balanceOf()</i>	Returns the number of tokens that a <i>BPAddr</i> holds.
	<i>transferFrom()</i>	Called by the <i>mint()</i> or <i>burn()</i> function when creating or deleting a token
	<i>totalSupply()</i>	The total amount of tokens
	<i>setApprovalForAll()</i>	Delegates management of the token to a <i>BPAddr</i>

3.2 Service Policy Definition

The creation of service policies within the blockchain is managed through the use of two smart contracts, known as the *identity* and *policy management* contracts. The *identity* smart contract uses the permissioned blockchain feature to register authorized endpoints within the blockchain. The identities of authorized endpoints are defined using a *struct*, as outlined in Eq. 1. The *struct* includes information such as the type of identity (*client* or *provider*), a *name* as a plaintext denomination, and a *desc* that is an optional attribute used to provide additional information to the registered identity.

$$identityStruct = \{(type, name, desc)\} \quad (1)$$

A relationship is established between the identity information and a specific *BPAddr* of authenticated endpoints through the creation of a key-value pair mapping as part of the *identity* smart contract functionality, as shown in Eq. 2. It is important to note that the authentication process for new endpoints is not covered in this research manuscript, and it is assumed that a suitable registration process for new clients/service providers is already in place.

$$mapping(BPAddr \Rightarrow identityStruct)Identities \quad (2)$$

The *policy management* smart contract is used to register information about roles and services, which is then utilized to create mappings that define a service policy. All the transactions are verified through blockchain events. An administrator-type user must be authorized by the *identity management* smart contract to interact with the blockchain through the *session management dApp* interface, requiring the use of proper blockchain keys for the execution of the

transactions. The sequence diagram in Fig. 3 outlines the process for creating a service policy, with the main steps being as follows:

Fig. 3 Policy definition sequence diagram

1. *registerRole()*: The process of creating a service policy involves an administrator registering the relevant roles that are approved for use inside the ZTN. The information for each role includes a human-readable name for the role (*roleTag*), a modifier used to set a time limit for the $\alpha\tau|\rho\tau$ (*roleMod*), and a unique identifier (*roleId*) used for creating the policy mappings.
2. *registerService()*: The administrator also registers the different types of services available in the ZTN. Each service must have a readable name that represents the service (*serviceTag*), and a unique identifier used for policy mappings (*serviceId*).
3. *definePolicy()*: A service policy is established by creating a relationship between a specific service, a service provider, and a group of roles. The structure of this policy includes a unique identifier (*policyId*), the service it pertains to (*serviceId*), the roles that have access to it (*roles[]*), the blockchain address of the service provider identity (*BAddr_{sp}*), and an additional attribute (*extraAtt*) that holds the hashed values of the policy. The *extraAtt* attribute, in particular, plays a crucial role in subsequent interactions within the system, especially during token verification procedures described in subsection 3.4.
4. *assignRoles()*: A mapping (*clientRoles*) is established between the blockchain public address of identities of type “client” (*BAddr_{cl}*) and a list of role ids (*roles[]*). The *clientRoles* mapping is affected by the defined

policy and determines which $BPaddr_{cl}$ is able to access a service, based on their assigned $roles[]$

3.3 Token Creation

The ZT&T session management mechanism automatically creates the session tokens on endpoints' connection requests. Figs. 4 and 5 illustrate the procedure of creation and transfer of the session tokens. The $tokenURI$ of the created tokens contains the values of the $tokenType$, $policyId$, $policyHash$, and $expTime$. The created $\alpha\tau$ and $\rho\tau$ are linked to a specific $policyId$, which determines the service being offered within the ZTN. The relation between the $\rho\tau$ and $\alpha\tau$ is 1:N. However, a single client can not possess more than one $\alpha\tau$ that matches a particular $policyId$.

Fig. 4 Provider session token creation and provision

The procedure of creating tokens for a *service provider* is illustrated in Fig. 4. The process is as follows:

1. The ZT&T system receives a connection from an entity of type Provider.
 - (a) The connection triggers the session token creation process.
2. The ZT&T system verifies the existing policies registered in the blockchain through the *session management dApp* mechanism.
 - (a) For every policy, it will verify if the $BPaddr_{sp}$ attribute value matches the Identity ($BPaddr$) of the service provider.
3. For every matching policy, a session token of type $\rho\tau$ is created.
 - (a) The $tokenURI$ of the created token reflects the matching policy.
 - (b) The $tokenType$ attribute is set to 2 to denote it is a session token of type *provider*.
 - (c) The $policyId$ attribute value is set to the id of the matching policy.
 - (d) The $policyHash$ attribute of the token is populated with the value of the *extraAtt* of the matched policy.
 - (e) The expiration time $expTime$ value of the $\rho\tau$ is set to the $roleMod$ value in seconds, for the role associated to the $BPaddr_{sp}$ identity.

4. The created session tokens of type “provider” are transferred to the connecting entity as an NFT transfer blockchain transaction.

Fig. 5 Access session token creation and provision

The procedure of creating tokens for a *client* is illustrated in Fig. 5. The process is as follows:

1. The ZT&T system receives a connection from an entity of type Client.
 - (a) The connection triggers the session token creation process.
2. The ZT&T system verifies the existing policies registered in the blockchain through the *session management dApp* mechanism.
 - (a) It verifies if the connecting Identity (*BPaddr*) has assigned roles by querying the *clientRoles* mapping in the blockchain.
 - (b) It verifies a match of every assigned role with the policy records.
3. For every matched role in a policy, a session token of type $\alpha\tau$ is created.
 - (a) The *tokenURI* of the created token reflects the matching policy.
 - (b) The *tokenType* attribute is set to 1 to denote it is a session token of type *client*.
 - (c) The *policyId* attribute value is set to the id of the matching policy.
 - (d) The *policyHash* attribute of the token is populated with the value of the *extraAtt* of the matched policy.
 - (e) The expiration time *expTime* value of the $\alpha\tau$ is set to the *roleMod* value in seconds, for the role associated to the *BPaddr_{cl}* identity.
4. The created session tokens of type “access” are transferred to the connecting entity as an NFT transfer blockchain transaction.

3.4 Token Verification

The purpose of the session tokens is to serve as an additional access verification by the secure network overlay. Once a token is created and a service session is

started, the overlay periodically verifies the “integrity” of the open sessions by checking *if a policy exists for a given token and the expiration time is greater than the current time*. Whenever one of these conditions is not met, the secure network overlay automatically ends the session, and the requesting service can no longer be accessed. The *SDP Controller* and the *session management* are responsible for checking the validity of $\alpha\tau|\rho\tau$. The *SDP Controller* can interrupt the sessions or deny access for entities that do not hold valid session tokens (e.g., expired or no matching policy exists). The verification logic is illustrated through pseudocode in Algorithm 1 and the process is explained as follows:

- When the *SDP controller* receives a connection request from a registered provider endpoint identified as $BPaddr_{sp}|BPaddr_{cl}$, the controller interacts with the session management dApp to validate the endpoint using the *validate(BPaddr)* API method. The request is signed with the *BPrK* of the endpoint, ensuring that it is securely tied to a *BPaddr*, thereby affirming the identity of the requesting entity in a cryptographically secure manner.
- The *session management dApp* checks the validity of the endpoint by determining if it is listed among the registered identities. The *isRegistered(BPaddr)* method returns a Boolean value (True|False) based on the information in the *Identities* mapping. If the return value is *False*, *validate(BPaddr)* returns an empty list of session tokens, and the *SDP controller* denies the connection.
- If the *isRegistered(BPaddr)* method returns *True*, the *ownedTokens(BPaddr)* method is executed and returns a list of all tokens owned by the entity making the connection request. The values of the *tokenURI* are examined for each token. The *expTime* must be greater than the current block timestamp, and the *policyHash* must match the *extraAtt* hash value of the policy registered on the blockchain. Tokens that are determined to be invalid are *burned*. If there are no valid tokens or the *ownedTokens(BPaddr)* function returns an empty list, the process is terminated, and the *SDP controller* denies the connection.
- When the *SDP controller* verifies that an entity holds valid $\alpha\tau|\rho\tau$, it establishes a secure overlay session per token. The session enables entities holding $\rho\tau$ to advertise its service on the network, on the other hand, entities holding $\alpha\tau$ are allowed to consume advertised services as long as the tokens remain valid.

The *session management dApp* continuously retrieves the information of open overlay sessions to get a list of identities ($BPaddr_{sp}|BPaddr_{cl}$) actively participating in service sessions. The validation process outlined in step 19 to 35 of Algorithm 1 is initiated for each token that belongs to identities with active sessions. Invalid tokens are burned, and the SDP controller is notified to terminate the service sessions for endpoints that do not possess valid $\alpha\tau|\rho\tau$.

Algorithm 1 Token verification

Input: *BPAddr*
Output: *hasValid[]*

```

1: procedure SDP_CONTROLLER_REQUESTS_VALIDATION_TO_SESSION_MAN-
   AGEMENT_DAPP
2:   hasValid[]  $\leftarrow$  validate(BPAddr)
3:   if hasValid[] is not empty then
4:     for t in hasValid[] do
5:       tokenURI  $\leftarrow$  tokenURI(t.tokenId)
6:       if tokenURI.tokenType == 2 then
7:         open provider session
8:         with policy(tokenURI.policyId)
9:       end if
10:      if tokenURI.tokenType == 1 then
11:        open client session
12:        with policy(tokenURI.policyId)
13:      end if
14:    end for
15:   else
16:     refuse connection
17:   end if
18: end procedure
19: procedure VALIDATE(BPADDR)
20:   validTokens[]  $\leftarrow$  []
21:   if isRegistered(BPAddr) then
22:     tokens[]  $\leftarrow$  ownedTokens(BPAddr)
23:     for t in tokens[] do
24:       tokenURI  $\leftarrow$  tokenURI(t.tokenId)
25:       if tokenURI.expTime > block.timestamp and
26:         tokenURI.policyHash == hashOf(tokenURI.policyId) then
27:         validTokens.push(t)
28:       else
29:         burn(t.tokenId)
30:       end if
31:     end for
32:     return validTokens
33:   else
34:     return validTokens
35:   end if
36: end procedure

```

Note:*BPAddr* - Public address of client/provider*hasValid[]* - List of valid tokens*Validate*(*BPAddr*) - Procedure handled by the session management dApp

4 Experiments and Results

4.1 Test-bed preparation

A prototype of the proposed system was built to demonstrate its functionality. The key components include a private Ethereum blockchain composed of five nodes based on the Hyperledger Besu project [32]. A Proof-of-Authority (PoA) consensus mechanism [33, 34] was set up to lower the computation demands of the blockchain. The smart contracts for the *ERC-721 tokens*, *identity*, and *policy management* were written in the Solidity programming language and deployed to the blockchain using the Remix IDE [35]. The *session management dApp* was developed in Python 3.8, using the Web3.py [36] libraries for blockchain-related operations (creating accounts, hashing, signing and sending transactions, and interacting with smart contracts) and Flask for handling API requests from the SDP controller.

The secure network overlay is managed by OpenZiti, a novel open-source Zero Trust platform developed by NetFoundry. In this platform, the SDP controller is referred to as the “ziti controller,” and the SDP Gateway is the “edge router.” OpenZiti was built using the Golang programming language. Only minor modifications were made to the controller’s functionality code to perform the experiments. An API request to the session management dApp was added to create, provision, and validate the session tokens alongside extra logic for opening and closing service sessions based on the metadata content of the tokens.

OpenZiti includes three types of policies: *service policies*, *service edge router policies*, and *edge router policies*. Only the *service policies* are closely related to the proposed system in this manuscript; the other policies are not considered in this scenario (they are set to allow all types of overlay traffic by default). Additionally, in the configuration of OpenZiti a *service policy* is established in two steps: *Bind* and *Dial*. The *Bind* step identifies the entity providing the service, and the *Dial* step specifies the clients permitted to access certain services. These steps are analogous to the service policy definition in the proposed system, as outlined in section 3.2 of this manuscript. To simplify the prototype deployment, the service policies are set up both in the ziti controller and the blockchain. The controller policies are used for the overlay functionality, and blockchain information is used for token validation.

Identities for endpoints have been configured in both the *blockchain* and the *ziti controller*. The unique identifier of the identities in the *ziti controller* corresponds to the *BPaddr* associated with each endpoint. All endpoints have been set up with a Web3.py client for handling blockchain transactions using an Ethereum account and have executed the *setApprovalForAll()* method to the *ERC-721 smart contract*, allowing the *session management dApp* to manage their tokens.

4.2 Experiment

Two service policies ($p1$ and $p2$) were set up using the method outlined in section 3.2. These policies grant access to different video services deployed as endpoints in the overlay network. Additionally, four distinct *roles* - *Provider*, *Executive*, *Subscriber*, and *Tester* - were established to differentiate among the various endpoints connecting to the ZTN. For this experiment, the *roleMod* attribute for the *Provider* role has a time limit of 24 hours from the block timestamp at the time of token creation, *Executive* has a time limit of 30 minutes, *Subscriber* has a limit of 5 minutes, and *Tester* has a limit of 1 minute. The experiment involves seven endpoints, with two functioning as video service providers and the remaining five as video clients. Out of the five video clients, three request the video service provided by $p1$, and the other two request the one provided by $p2$. The video service providers have been assigned the *Provider* role. For the video clients, two are assigned the *Tester* role, two hold the *Executive* role, and one holds the *Subscriber* role. Table 3 showcases the configuration of the policies and service tokens. The steps of the experiment are described as follows:

1. The *session management dApp* generates and distributes $\alpha\tau|\rho\tau$ to the *BPAddr* of entities subject to the service policies upon receiving connection requests from the *SDP Controller*.
2. The entities that possess $\rho\tau$ are authorized to initiate a connection with the network to promote their video service.
3. Simultaneously, the clients with valid $\alpha\tau$ request a service session.

The impact of session token expiration on the five client sessions is demonstrated in Fig. 6 over an 1860-second (31-minute) time frame. It can be seen that the clients with the roles *Tester*, *Subscriber*, and *Executive* have their sessions automatically terminated at the 60 seconds, 300 seconds, and 1800 seconds marks, respectively.

Fig. 6 Client session behavior over time

Table 3 Service policy and token configuration

Policy ¹	<i>p1</i>	“video1”, [“exec”, “sub”, “test”], “0xValue1”, “hash1”
	<i>p2</i>	“video2”, [“exec”, “test”], “0xValue2”, “hash2”
Tokens ²	$\rho\tau 1$	{“tokenType”: 2, “policyId”: <i>p1</i> , “policyHash”: “hash1”, “expTime” ³ : timestamp + 86400}
	$\rho\tau 2$	{“tokenType”: 2, “policyId”: <i>p2</i> , “policyHash”: “hash2”, “expTime” ³ : timestamp + 86400}
	$\alpha\tau 1$	{“tokenType”: 1, “policyId”: <i>p1</i> , “policyHash”: “hash1”, “expTime” ³ : timestamp + 1800}
	$\alpha\tau 2$	{“tokenType”: 1, “policyId”: <i>p1</i> , “policyHash”: “hash1”, “expTime” ³ : timestamp + 300}
	$\alpha\tau 3$	{“tokenType”: 1, “policyId”: <i>p1</i> , “policyHash”: “hash1”, “expTime” ³ : timestamp + 60}
	$\alpha\tau 4$	{“tokenType”: 1, “policyId”: <i>p2</i> , “policyHash”: “hash2”, “expTime” ³ : timestamp + 1800}
	$\alpha\tau 5$	{“tokenType”: 1, “policyId”: <i>p2</i> , “policyHash”: “hash2”, “expTime” ³ : timestamp + 60}

¹Notation: *policyId*, *serviceId*, *roles*[], *BPaddr_{sp}*, *extraAtt*²Notation: *tokenId*, *tokenURI*³*expTime* Unix timestamp in UTC format.

The session token expiration’s effectiveness is evident in Fig. 6 as the number of active sessions gradually decreases over time. To further demonstrate the flexibility of the mechanism, the *expTime* of the provider tokens associated with policy *p1* is set to 240 seconds from the block timestamp at the time of token creation. As a result, all sessions controlled by *p1* are terminated at the 240-second mark, causing all client connections to be closed and denying access to the service, as shown in Fig. 7. This highlights that our proposed mechanism can also affect the session connections from the service provider’s point of view, allowing for specific services to have a predefined lifespan within the network.

The system’s performance, measured in time (s), is presented in Fig. 8 for different block time configurations, namely 2s, 5s, and 15s. Notably, ‘block time’ refers to the configured interval at which new blocks are produced in Hyper Ledger Besu blockchain deployment, influencing transaction processing speed and system throughput. The most time-consuming tasks involve executing transactions on the blockchain. Tasks performed manually, such as creating policies, are not considered for this measure. On the other hand, the performance of the automatic tasks for creating and provisioning $\alpha\tau|\rho\tau$, as well as validating and burning tokens may affect the system’s overall execution as they may incur delays in establishing and terminating sessions. The test was

Fig. 7 Provider session behavior over time

carried out for 100 transactions that created new session tokens and was measured from the moment a transaction was submitted to the point when it was confirmed in the blockchain. The results highlight the variation in transaction processing time as the block time increases, which can be attributed to the specific timing of transaction execution relative to the closing of the block time window, the number of transactions included in the same block and the time it takes to propagate the block to the other nodes in the blockchain. Under worst-case conditions, individual transactions can consume the entire block time. Reducing the block time of the blockchain deployment could improve system performance. However, it may also increase the risk of losing block synchronization if the number of P2P nodes connected to the blockchain increases [37].

Fig. 8 Transaction processing time in the blockchain

A series of tests for each block time configuration (2s, 5s, 15s) were conducted based on distinct transaction execution rates: 1 transaction per second (TPS), 10 TPS, and 100 TPS. The execution rate was constrained by a Python script that executed the token creation transaction at different intervals. These tests visually represent the behavior of the blockchain when processing the

transactions. Figs. 9 to 14 encapsulate the results of these tests. Two metrics are presented for each block time configuration: transaction pool and transactions per block.

Fig. 9 Transaction pool behavior in a block time of 2 seconds

Fig. 10 Transaction pool behavior in a block time of 5 seconds

The transaction pool metric, as depicted in Figs. 9, 10, and 11 showcases the number of transactions awaiting in the pool before being added to a block. It provides insights into the system's efficiency in handling transaction loads, especially when the transaction execution rate is high. Notably, as the block time increases, there is a discernible slowdown in processing transactions from the pool. Consequently, transactions tend to accumulate in the pool, awaiting processing, leading to potential delays. This behavior highlights the balance between block time configuration and system responsiveness, particularly in scenarios with high transaction demands.

Figs. 12, 13, and 14 present the transactions per block metric, which shows the number of transactions included in each block. This metric offers a perspective on the system's capacity to process and confirm transactions within the specified block time. The transaction execution rate directly impacts the number of transactions included in a block. A higher transaction rate can lead to

Fig. 11 Transaction pool behavior in a block time of 15 seconds

blocks being filled more quickly, but it also means there's a greater likelihood of transactions waiting in the pool if the block's capacity is exceeded.

Fig. 12 Transactions per block in a block time of 2 seconds

Furthermore, blocks have a longer window to accumulate transactions as the block time increases, potentially leading to a full block. However, this comes at a cost: a longer block time means that individual transactions may have to wait longer to be confirmed. This trade-off between block time and transaction processing speed is critical in the system's design and configuration.

The results highlight the system's responsiveness. As the transaction execution rate increases, the transaction pool's behavior and the number of transactions per block provide valuable insights into the system's scalability and potential bottlenecks. It's evident that as the block time decreases, the system's ability to handle higher transaction rates improves, but it also brings forth challenges in maintaining synchronization, especially when the network of P2P nodes expands.

Table 4 compares the proposed ZT&T blockchain-based session tokens and the conventional use of cookies and session tokens. The security of session management is crucial, and the ZT&T blockchain-based session tokens exhibit a heightened level of security, primarily attributed to the inherent security

Fig. 13 Transactions per block in a block time of 5 seconds

Fig. 14 Transactions per block in a block time of 15 seconds

features of blockchain technology. This robustness makes them highly resistant to tampering. In contrast, traditional cookies and session tokens present more vulnerabilities. They are susceptible to various risks, including session hijacking, cookie theft, and cross-site script inclusion (XSSI).

Our implementation uses immutable record-keeping when considering the persistence and expiration of session tokens. This ensures that tokens cannot be maliciously or accidentally extended beyond their intended lifespan. On the other hand, traditional methods, which rely heavily on server-side mechanisms, can introduce vulnerabilities if not implemented with precision.

Regarding transparency and auditability, the blockchain records associated with the ZT&T tokens provide a clear advantage. They offer a transparent and auditable trail, ensuring high accountability and traceability. While traditional methods have the capability to maintain logs, they often lack the immutability and transparency that come inherently with a blockchain.

Addressing scalability and performance, it is evident that blockchain-based tokens offer many advantages but are not without challenges. They can experience latency, especially during interactions that require a blockchain transaction. Traditional cookies and session tokens are generally faster in operation but might still face scalability issues if the underlying server infrastructure is not robust enough.

Table 4 Comparison of blockchain-based session tokens vs. standard approaches

Criteria	ZT&T Session Tokens	Blockchain-based	Traditional Cookies & Session Tokens
Security	Resistant to tampering due to blockchain's inherent security.		Susceptible to session hijacking, cookie theft, and XSSI.
Persistence & Expiry	Transparent and immutable record of token validity and expiration on the blockchain.		Rely on server-side mechanisms; potential vulnerabilities if not implemented correctly.
Transparency & Auditability	Transparent and auditable trail due to blockchain records.		Can maintain logs but lack blockchain's immutability and transparency.
Scalability & Performance	Potential latency during high network congestion.		Generally faster but might face scalability issues with inadequate server infrastructure.

The work presented in this manuscript attains a secure and transparent solution for session management, effectively addressing many of the security limitations inherent in traditional methods.

Table 5 Comparison of research using blockchain-based tokens

scheme	anonymous	policy-based	expiration	gasCost
Hussain et al. [22]	-	X	X	-
Lyu et al. [27]	✓	✓	✓	442,006
ZT&T	✓	✓	✓	359,765

Table 5 offers a comparative analysis of various blockchain-based token schemes, emphasizing features such as anonymity, policy-based mechanisms, expiration, and gas costs. The scheme proposed by Hussain et al. incorporates the user identification (UID) within the token composition. Although this UID is hashed, the token also includes the Ethereum address of both the user and the device they connect with. This reveals both endpoints. While the Ethereum address does offer a degree of anonymity, the exposure of both endpoints is a concern. Furthermore, the manuscript does not disclose the actual gas costs associated with the tokens. The scheme lacks a policy-based implementation, and its tokens do not have an expiration feature. In contrast, the scheme by Lyu et al. covers all these features and has a gas cost of 359,765, which accounts for the added cost of creating and verifying the tokens. The ZT&T scheme is similar to Lyu et al. in feature set but has a reduced gas cost of 379,353. This reduction is attributed to the token verification using the ERC-721 standard for NFTs, allowing verifications to be conducted by querying

the blockchain without requiring a blockchain transaction. The details of the session tokens are illustrated in Fig. 15 in the form of a log extracted from the REMIX IDE, where the transaction cost for the creation and transfer of the token alongside the token information is shown. The anonymity of the user is preserved by using the *BPAddr* as the token receiver in the ‘address_to’ field without disclosing any private details. The association with the policy and the expiration time are part of the ‘tokenURI’ field of the session token.

```

status      0x1 Transaction mined and execution succeed
transaction hash  0xe69948a02309de92360ef378aa3151c858f9a10a6b17100c6c45c2889440d4
block hash    0x24b65846d6c4b5a7917c31e6a175bdf139eb23f796b5f30bbb48d028dff94f4
block number  15156
from         0xfe3b557e8fb62b89f4916b721be55ceb828dbd73
to          sessionSmartContract.mint(address,uint256,string,string)
           0x4245cf4518cb2c280f5e9c6a03c90c147f80b4d9
gas         gas
transaction cost  359765 gas Gas
input       0x2fb...d7d00
decoded input
{
  "address_to": "0xe6393E132111CBa0f1332088a9802680A3347702",
  "uint256_tokenId": "2",
  "string_tokenType": "1",
  "string tokenURI": "{\"tokenType\": 1, \"policyId\": p1, \"policyHash\": \"0x98968199bb1197fbf353e0b9dbc838406b84c317536329fcf8891a414dd2c8ff\", \"expTime\": 1702533926}"
}
decoded output  - Session Token Information
logs          [
  {
    "from": "0x4245cf4518cb2c280f5e9c6a03c90c147f80b4d9",
    "topic": "0xdddf252ad1be2c89b69c2b068fc378daa952ba7f163c4a11628f55a4df523b3ef",
    "event": "Transfer",
    "args": {
      "0": "0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000",
      "1": "0xe6393E132111CBa0f1332088a9802680A3347702",
      "2": "4",
      "from": "0x0000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000",
      "to": "0xe6393E132111CBa0f1332088a9802680A3347702",
      "tokenId": "4"
    }
  }
]

```

Fig. 15 Session token creation transaction log from REMIX IDE

5 Conclusion

This paper presented a secure method for managing service sessions in ZTNs using blockchain-based tokens. ERC-721 non-fungible tokens (NFTs) ensure that only authorized entities can initiate service sessions in a ZTN. Additionally, the Zero Trust model’s requirement for constant verification is met through blockchain-based policies associated with the public address (*BPAddr*) of entities involved in them. The session management is maintained securely

by automatically verifying token expiration time and the integrity of the policy configuration through hash validation. The use of blockchain also provides benefits such as data storage resilience, an immutable historical ledger, and programmatic access to stored data through smart contracts.

Despite the potential benefits, there are still concerns about the system's performance if the entire configuration of the SDP controller is migrated to the blockchain. Additional testing is needed to gauge the impact of a full blockchain implementation on overlay operations. Additionally, the process of creating policies is manual, requiring an administrator to work with the *session management dApp*. Further research could explore using Intent-Based Networking (IBN) to create automatic service policies while maintaining overall system management [38]. Furthermore, the metadata of the $\alpha\tau|\rho\tau$ could be expanded to include additional attributes that could affect the Quality of Service (QoS) of specific service sessions. Additionally, synchronization techniques could be employed to automatically configure the network overlay based on confirmed blockchain data by utilizing the blockchain event information.

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Declarations

Conflict of interest/Competing interests

All authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript. The authors have no competing interests to declare relevant to this article's content.

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